

An Automated Robotic Gripper Design Framework

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Abstract—Grippers act as the physical link between robotic manipulators and their surroundings, allowing robots to handle objects and perform a variety of tasks, such as the manipulation of grapes during harvesting. To improve the design of grippers, we propose an automated framework, which starts with an initial design that resembles human hands' configuration during grape harvesting and optimizes it based on the characteristics of the grape variety to be harvested. In this direction, the proposed framework utilizes parametric models for both the grape and the gripper and integrates them into an automated grasp planning simulation procedure. All the components are combined in a custom graphical user interface (GUI), making the entire process more user-friendly. Results from our experimentation showed that the proposed framework has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of gripper design, especially for applications involving the handling of objects with unique parameters and requirements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Grippers are an essential component of robotic arms that enable robots to manipulate objects and perform various tasks in fields such as manufacturing, logistics, healthcare, and agriculture. In order to manipulate different objects, recent research [1] [2] focused on acquiring complex control strategies that utilize a universal gripper, rather than designing new custom ones. Although these studies have significantly enhanced the dexterous manipulation control algorithms, there has been minimal research on utilizing data-driven methods for gripper hardware design. Although task-specific grippers are frequently used in real-world robotic applications, the manual design process can be time-consuming and heavily reliant on engineers' knowledge and experience. This can hinder the rapid adaptation to changes in tasks and applications.

Various techniques have been used for creating fingers with complementary geometry to the objects being manipulated, such as heuristic imprinting [3]. However, this approach requires extensive manual adjustment periods to function correctly and is not robust to changes in object orientation.

Wolniakowski et al. [4] have improved the parameterized geometry of a basic cuboid gripper for automated finger design by utilizing different gripper quality measures derived in simulation. Taylor and Rodriguez [5] adjusted the end-effector's motion trajectory and curvature to increase the throwing distance. However, determining an appropriate parameterization strategy is a complex process that frequently results in a highly constrained design space. On the other hand, Huy Ha et al. [6] have presented a model that is

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Fig. 1: [Top Left] Human hand interaction with grapes during harvesting. [Top Right] Initial curved gripper finger design based on observations made by examining human interactions with grape bunches on a Robotiq 2F-85 gripper. [Bottom Left] Re-design for real grapes. [Bottom Right] Re-design for synthetic grapes.

capable of exploring the whole 3D geometric space by using Truncated Signed Distance Functions (TSDF) [7] to describe 3D geometry.

To assess the efficiency of the produced gripper design, various metrics are used to measure the grasp quality achieved with the gripper. Most research methods on robot grasping have utilized analytical [8] or learned grasp quality metrics to select and assess grasping poses [9] [10]. However, these methods frequently ignore the dynamic grasping process and environmental limitations, making them less transferable to the actual world [11]. Dexnet-2.0 proposed by Mahler et al. [12] utilized deep neural networks to predict grasp quality but is based on the assumption of a fixed gripper design.

This study presents a resilient framework to generate

Fig. 2: The BACCHUS automated gripper design framework architecture.

designs that are easily customized to achieve robust grasps in real-world scenarios, such as robotic grape harvesting. In this context, the knowledge that can be extracted from human hands during grape harvesting can be a valuable source of information for gripper design. The way that humans grasp and manipulate grapes can provide insights into the most effective gripper fingertip design for the task. To leverage this knowledge, we propose an automated gripper design framework that takes inspiration from human demonstration data. An initial gripper model was created, utilizing human demonstrations, and observing the way human hands interact with grape bunches during harvesting. This has allowed us to create an initial fingertip design that closely mimics the way human hands grasp grape clusters. However, unique parameters and requirements must be considered for each grape variety in order to ensure that the gripper is suitable for grasping.

To address this issue, we propose the BACCHUS Automated Gripper Design Framework, whose main contributions are summarized as follows:

- To incorporate information extracted from human demonstrations to the automated optimization process
- To utilize parametric models for both the grape and the gripper
- To integrate the extracted models with an automated grasp planning simulation procedure
- To combine all the above in a custom graphical user interface (GUI) in order to make the whole procedure

more user friendly

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Harvesting both wine and table grapes is a delicate procedure, since damaged grapes cannot be included in wine making or be sold as table grapes in the market. Towards this end, we propose the BACCHUS Automated Gripper Design Framework, which incorporates an automated optimization and adjustment process with user knowledge, and simulation. A summary of the proposed framework architecture can be seen in Figure 2. The interaction with the user is enabled through a custom GUI. The grape variety and its attributes are provided by the user and the parametric models for both the grape bunch and the gripper fingertips are loaded to the system and are automatically adjusted in accordance to the selected variety parameters. These parameters can vary from grape variety to grape variety, such as e.g. average size of the grape bunch, the individual grape average size, and the density of berries on the bunch. The parametric gripper model's length, width, and curvature are adjusted automatically in order to conform with the average cluster dimensions of the selected grape variety. Additionally, the parametric grape model parameters are automatically adjusted to match the ones of the selected variety. The user can then further adjust the parametric models or continue directly to the grasp simulation, where a uniform sampling on the grape bunch 3D model is performed to generate a set of possible grasp positions. The gripper 3D model is used for generating the

Fig. 3: [Top] Variations of the parametric model for the grapes. [Bottom] Variations of the parametric model for the gripper fingertips.

possible grasp orientations for each grasp position. Thus, the initial set of grasp poses is generated.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Initial Gripper Design

During the initial gripper design phase, we considered how humans interact with grape bunches during the harvesting process. By studying experts at vineyards, we were able to make assumptions about the ideal shape for our gripper design. We observed how human hands interacted with grapes and the specific finger configurations experts used to grasp them. Based on this research, we decided to go with a curved finger design (as shown in Figure 1), with its curvature selected based on actual measurements of grape bunches from sample grape varieties at hand. This design enables the gripper to pick up objects with various circumferences within a range.

B. Parametric Models

To create the parametric models for the grapes and gripper fingertips, we utilized Blender open-source software [13]. First, for the grapes, a basic model was created using Blender’s modelling tools and geometry nodes. For the gripper fingertips parametric model, we utilized the initial 3D model as a base. Then, using the software’s parametric modelling features to add various parameters to the models (Figure 3). Overall, the grape parametric model was designed to allow for customization of eight different characteristics, including the size and shape of both individual grapes and the bunch as a whole, as well as the strain on the stem, the location of the grapes on the bunch, their roundness, color, density, and girth. By adjusting these parameters we

are able to test for different grape varieties, where the overall size, density and size of grape clusters vary between them. Similarly, the parametric model of gripper fingertips can be customized for overall size, curvature, and the distance between the fingertip bases. These models can be used separately in Blender for quick 3D model generation during testing, and are also embedded in the automated gripper design GUI during deployment.

C. Custom Graphical User Interface

A custom GUI was developed for the BACCHUS automatic gripper design framework, where open source tools (e.g. Blender) and tools already available through ROS (e.g. Gazebo [14]) were embedded, in order to present the proposed framework in a coherent and user-friendly way. The initial screen allows the user to choose from existing models and grape varieties or create a new one. Upon selecting grape variety the framework proposes: either an existing gripper model that suits the parameters of the selected variety (average cluster dimensions, grape density etc.), or informs the user that no viable model exists in the database, and prompts the creation of a new one. The user can view various information about the selected variety and gripper model, including grape variety description, average dimensions, and the dimensions of the selected fingertip design. If the user chooses to create a new gripper model or add a new grape variety, the basic parametric grape model is loaded into the GUI, allowing the user to adjust parameters and see real-time deformations. The user can then adjust the parameters of the gripper fingertips and see the impact on the model in real time.

After saving the newly configured 3D models for both grape and gripper fingertip, the user is guided to the simulation tab. There, the Gazebo simulation environment is loaded that includes a vine tree with several instances of the grape bunch 3d model attached to it, and a UR10e robotic manipulator with the newly saved gripper fingertip design attached to its end effector. Inside this environment (Figure 4) the user can visualize the performance evaluation of different grasps using the new fingertip design. The overall surface-on-surface contact between the gripper and the grape clusters is analyzed to determine the effectiveness of the gripper fingertip design in producing viable grasps.

D. Grasp Pose List Generation

In order to generate the initial set of grasp poses a truncated cone primitive is fitted on the 3d model of the grape bunch. Uniform sampling is then performed on the surface of the truncated cone to select a uniform point cloud all around the grape bunch, with each point corresponding to a possible position for the center of the gripper while grasping. All this positions comprise the initial set of grasp poses. Taking into account the nature of the task at hand, and physical properties of the grape clusters while on the vine tree, this initial set of poses is pruned to remove the extreme poses, since grasping the bunch from either end will not produce stable grasps. This pruned set is now the new initial

Fig. 4: The BACCHUS automated gripper design framework GUI. General information regarding the selected grape and gripper models are being presented in the first tab (left). Then the grape and gripper fingertip parametric models are presented in the following tabs. In the simulation tab (right) of BACCHUS Gripper Design GUI. The selected models are loaded inside the Gazebo simulation tab to be evaluated.

poses set, which are then tested in the simulation for their feasibility.

The 3D model of a grape bunch is created to represent an average sized bunch of the particular variety. The variations in size and shape for this grape variety are taken into account and used to generate a range of scaled 3D models. The initial set of grasp poses are then tested with these models, and the poses where the gripper cannot hold the grape bunch properly are discarded. This is done to ensure that the grasp pose set is applicable to most grape bunches of this variety early on in the process.

The grasp poses that passed the scale test are then tested in a simulated environment where a robotic platform and vine are present. Grasp motions are planned and executed for all simulated grape bunches that are within the robot's workspace. For each grape bunch that the robot can reach, all possible grasp poses are attempted, and a score based on the feasibility of each pose is determined by evaluating the success of the motion plans for all reachable grape bunches. Any grasp poses that fail to produce any successful motion plan are eliminated, these poses are mainly the ones that require the robotic arm to be in contact with either the vines of the trunk of the vine tree which are marked as obstacles. Leaves are not marked as obstacles, since touching the leaves will not damaged the robotic arm or the grape bunch.

$$feasibility\ score = \frac{\#successful\ motions}{\#grape\ bunches}$$

The final grasp pose set along with its score is saved and used for the evaluation of the gripper design.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The evaluation process comprised of 3 separate stages: i) initial design and evaluation phase for the basic gripper model, ii) evaluation of the models produced by the framework with real grapes in lab conditions, and iii) field evaluation of the produced models during grape harvesting.

A. Initial Design & Evaluation of the Basic Gripper Model

At the initial stages of the evaluation, a modular variation of the prototype basic gripper fingertip design was 3D-printed and attached to a 2-jaw parallel electric Zimmer gripper on a KUKA manipulator (Figure 5). The gripper was used to grasp synthetic (plastic) grape bunches from a mockup tree setup designed by the Robotics Lab of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. These preliminary tests identified weaknesses in certain sections of the design, which led to the first redesign of the basic model.

For the second iteration of the basic gripper model, the modular approach was abandoned, and the finger tips were made sturdier to enable the gripper to maintain the grasp. Real grapes were utilized to evaluate the basic model's performance (Figure 5). This testing iteration resulted in another redesign of the basic model with less curvature, leading to the third and final basic model variation (Figure 1).

B. Evaluation with Real Grapes in Lab Conditions

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the framework to produce models capable of grasping gently grape clusters, and maintain the grasp, we performed an experiment in lab conditions with table grapes of two different varieties. The appropriate gripper design variations for the attributes of the selected varieties were produced from the framework, 3d printed and tested in the lab. The experiment involved two different bunches of each variety, and six variations

Grape Variety	Bunch circumference (cm)	Bunch length (cm)	Avg minimum % for grasping	Avg maximum % for grasping without damaging
Red Table Grapes	11	12	79.7%	90.3%
	13	15	78.7%	87.0%
White Table Grapes	12	20	81.0%	90.7%
	13	26	75.5%	88.0%

TABLE I: Second iteration of basic fingertip model geometry evaluation using real grapes.

Fig. 5: The various basic model iterations evaluation. [Top row] The evaluation of the the basic model using synthetic and real grapes. [Bottom row] The evaluation of the produced gripper models using real grapes in an actual vineyard in various conditions of clutter and defoliation.

of grasps for each bunch, including two angles and three different positions along the length of the bunch. The primary objective of this experiment was to evaluate the geometry of the fingertips and ensure that the bunches could be indeed grasped by each design without damaging the grapes. During the experiment, the gripper was fully opened, and we began closing it incrementally until we achieved a secure grasp of the bunch. We then continued to close the gripper until we observed some damage appearing on the grapes. This helped us to determine the maximum percentage of closing required for securely grasping the grapes without causing any damage using each geometry. The results of the experiment were recorded and can be seen in Table I. One of the primary difficulties we encountered during the gripper design was the need to customize it for grape bunches of varying sizes, which could vary considerably even within a single grape variety. We tackled this problem by reducing the curvature of the fingertips of the basic design, which allowed for a greater opening and enhanced flexibility to accommodate grapes of different girths. The data gathered from this experiment lead to the third and final iteration of the basic fingertip model, to ensure its effectiveness in grasping grapes without causing any damage. We devised a basic fingertip design that facilitates the modification of the length of the finger base based on the average girth of the grape variety being targeted. This feature enables us to create fingertips that are customized to the specific needs of each grape variety, ensuring optimal performance across a broad range of grasping scenarios.

C. Field Evaluation During Harvesting

The final stage of evaluation was conducted during the pilot trials and field testing of BACCHUS in the harvesting season of 2023. The BACCHUS automated gripper design framework was used to generate gripper variations for real and synthetic grapes, since the evaluation started early in the spring, when the real grapes were not present in the vineyard. And as the season progressed and the vineyard reached more mature stages, the plastic props were replaced by their real counterparts. The iterative process of evaluation and re-design took into account problems surfacing during field-testing, and help adjusting to the evolving needs of the vineyard. For example, handling more mature grapes required more careful grasps, so we used the parametric models to quickly adjust the size and curvature of the selected fingers and new fingertips were produced, 3d printed, and were available in the field for testing within 1-2 days. The changes performed based on the feedback from field testing included geometry and practicality changes such as:

- Size reduction to maneuver easily through vines
- Gripping force reduction to avoid damaging over mature grapes
- Curvature change to maintain the grasp with reduced force
- Grid of silicone addition to increase grip (Figure 1)

During the field evaluation the goal was to determine if the finger designs produced by the proposed framework were capable of gentle but secure grasps of various grape varieties. Overall, during the pilot deployment 95 trials were conducted in total, where in every trial the targeted cluster was first

grasped and then harvested autonomously by the robot. The initial detection of the grape cluster was performed using the cameras on the robotic platform and vision based algorithms. The grasping pose was extracted based on the obstacles and the reachability of the robot, and then the gripper approached the grape cluster and initiated grasping. The gripper (Robotiq 2f 85) was equipped with a force/torque sensor, that was utilized to determine if the grasp was achieved. During the trials, the BACCHUS platform performed selective harvested of grape bunches for 5 different varieties utilising gripper designs produced by the framework. The capability of the produced gripper designs to perform secure grasps, was measured to 94% (89 out of 95 cases), which was the amount of successful grasps performed during the experiments.

To access how gently the grasps were, since this was not something we could directly measure we employed the following strategy to determine if damage occurred. If the grasping was not maintained, so the grape cluster fell during transfer, or if the cluster had visual damage from the gripping force, then the grape cluster was deemed as damaged. Using this strategy we concluded that the percentage of damaged grapes was only about 2.3%. These results were promising, demonstrating the effectiveness of the automated gripper design framework in creating customized grippers for specific tasks.

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

We introduced the BACCHUS Automated Gripper Design Framework, which takes inspiration from human demonstration data to generate designs that can be easily customized to achieve robust grasps in real-world scenarios. The proposed framework incorporates an automated optimization and adjustment process with user knowledge and simulation. The user provides the grape variety and its attributes, and the parametric models for both the grape bunch and the gripper fingertips are loaded into the system and automatically adjusted according to the selected variety parameters. The framework generates a set of possible grasp positions through uniform sampling on the grape bunch 3D model, and the gripper 3D model is used for generating the possible grasp orientations for each grasp position. The initial set of grasp poses is generated, which can be further adjusted by the user. The proposed framework aimed to make the whole procedure more user-friendly through a custom graphical user interface (GUI). Various evaluation iterations resulted in a basic model for gripper fingertips, that was easily customized and tested both in lab and real field conditions during the field testing and harvesting pilot trials of the BACCHUS project in spring and summer of 2023. The evaluation indicate that the framework has the potential to create custom-made gripper fingertips tailored to specific tasks and applications, with a high degree of adaptability and efficiency.

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